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Evaluation of the Transgenic Potato Plantlets in Hydroponic Culture for Salt Tolerance

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Introduction:

The agricultural crop yield has been lessened due to the adverse effect of global warming and climate change whereas, 25% of total irrigated land has been drastically worsened by excess of salinity. Moreover, the ratio of salinity increases rapidly and it has been expected that 50% of all agricultural acreage would be grasped by salinization (Ashraf, 2004) [1]. This discouraging state could be reduced by enhancing the stress tolerance of the important crops. Today, potato is grown in 125 countries and more than a billion people worldwide consume it on a daily basis (Mullins *et al.*, 2006) [2]. It is envisaged as most salt sensitive plant and only 50 mM NaCl in the soil nutrients can lessen 50% of growth and yield of potato crop (Sayari *et al.*, 2005) [3]. Similarly, continuous exposure to low temperature also adversely affects the potato plant growth (Evers *et al.*, 2007) [4]. Environmental stresses are well known to negatively affect crop productivity; these stresses can reduce average yields of major crop plants by more than 50% (Wang *et al.*, 2003). The situation becomes worst in the scenario of global warming and climate change. Worldwide, 25% of total irrigated acreage has been adversely affected by salt. This situation is expected to get even worse as, by year 2050, more than 50% of all arable lands is estimated to be affected by salinization (Ashraf, 2004). This daunting situation demands the improvement of environmental stress tolerance of important food crops, especially those having potential to resolve food security issues. Today, potato is grown in 125 countries and more than a billion people worldwide consume it on a daily basis (Mullins *et al.*, 2006). Potato is at 4th most important food crop after wheat, maize and rice (Newell *et al.*, 1991). Traditional breeding has been extensively used for crop improvement however this approach is too much time consuming; 15 years are required to develop a potato cultivar by classical breeding (Mullins *et al.*, 2006) [5]. Attempts have been made to develop germplasm more tolerant to abiotic stresses through genetic improvement using biotechnological approaches. (Sakamoto and Murata, 2002) [12]; Park *et al.*, 2004; [6]. Different genes of varying functions from osmoprotectants to reactive oxygen (ROS) scavenging have been utilized to improve potato plants tolerance (Jeong *et al.*, 2001; [7] Sayari *et al.*, 2005; [8]. Tang *et al.* (2010) [10] used sodium proton antiporter gene *TrNHX1* from a leguminous forage *Trifolium repens* L. Their integration and successful expression was determined using reverse transcriptase PCR and RACE. They found that *TrNHX1* has a vacuolar Na⁺/H⁺-antiporter role and extrudes excess NaCl to the vacuole thus plays an important role in salt tolerance and ion homeostasis in *T. repens*. Xing *et al.* (2010) [11] genetically improved soybean crop by integration of *AtNHX1* gene through *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*. The transformed plant lines exhibited great tolerance to salt hence it was concluded that this gene could be used in agriculture crops to improve their salt tolerance level.

Materials and Methods

Plant material

The *in vitro* developed transgenic potato plantlets of variety Asterix and Sante carrying *AtNHX1* gene along with their wild type (non transgenic) potato plantlets were evaluated for salt tolerance under hydroponic culture. Three transgenic plantlets developed by *Agrobacterium* mediated gene transformation using bacterial plasmid *pBI* 121 harboring *AtNHX1* under control of *CaMV* 35S promoter. The transgenic potato plant lines of variety Asterix were designated with codes (A5, A7 and A8) and Sante (S5, S7 and S8). These were used as experimental plant material in the current study. The plantlets were shifted to the hydroponic culture for salt stress. Salt stress was applied to the experimental material of potato varieties as given in the Table 1.

Morpho-physiological parameters

The potato plant plantlets under hydroponic culture were assessed for various morphological characters along with several physiological traits.

Statistical Analysis

The experimental data was statistically analyzed by Complete Randomized Design (CRD) with two factors, 4 NaCl treatments and 3 replications. Factorial analysis of variance was carried out with the help of computerized software Statistics 8.1 (Analytical Software 2005) [12]. Moreover, the significant means were compared pair wisely using Least Significance Difference (LSD) test at 0.5 level of probability by statistical software.

Results and Discussion

1. Plant height

Plant height of the tested varieties under NaCl treatments at different levels (Table 1) revealed that all transgenic potato lines of both Asterix and Sante responded significantly to NaCl stress treatments. The maximum plant height (30.16 cm) was noted in transgenic variety Asterix (A5) followed by transgenic variety Sante (S5) with 28.83 cm up to 60 mM NaCl stress. Sante S5 plants produced 26.83 cm tall plants whereas; S7 and S8 developed 26.83, and 25.49 cm plant height respectively. Furthermore, Asterix A7 and A8 plants produced 25.5 cm and 26.33 cm plant height. Non transgenic plants of variety Sante (S0) developed most dwarf (10.58 cm) followed by non transgenic plants of Asterix i.e. A0, (12.33 cm) and were observed as the most susceptible ones among the tested plants. Additionally the tested plants showed highly significant differences at different levels of NaCl stress. Maximum (29.37 cm) plant height was recorded at 20 mM (29.91 cm) followed by control (29.37). Plants height was reduced to 19.62 cm at 40 mM NaCl and 14.12 cm at 60 mM NaCl. Our results were in conformity with the findings of Maryam Qayyum and Kunwar Shoaib (2013) [16] who reported reduced plant height in potato due to NaCl stress. Control plantlets of both varieties died after 1 week of stress while the transgenic varieties survived for 6 weeks. (Raque Folgado, *et al.*, (2013) [17]; Yanling Zang and Danielle J. Donnelly (1997) [18] also reported reduced, shoot length and overall growth traits in potato plantlets grown under NaCl at 80 and 120 mM concentration.

2. Number of nodes plant-1

The tested transgenic potato lines harboring *AtNHX1* gene and their respective control plants from both varieties Asterix and Sante responded differently for number of nodes plant-1 at different levels of NaCl (Table 1). Maximum (12.75) nodes plant-1 was studied in Sante transgenic line S5 followed by A8 (12.33). Asterix event

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A5 formed 11.41 nodes plant⁻¹ whereas A7 and S7 each exhibited 11.08 nodes plant⁻¹. A0 produced 7.66 and S0 developed least (6.33) nodes plant⁻¹. Various levels of NaCl also affected all potato plants but non transgenic plants were severely affected number of nodes plant⁻¹. Maximum (13.16) nodes plant⁻¹ were recorded at 20 mM NaCl stress while at control (12.07), at 40 mM (9.66) and at 60 mM NaCl minimum (6.79) number of nodes plant⁻¹ were studied. Transgenic Asterix and Sante responded differently for number of nodes plant⁻¹ even at 40 mM and 60 mM NaCl whereas, their wild type plantlet died even at 10 mM NaCl stress level. Shuji Yokoi, *et al.*, (2002) [19] reported retarded growth in crop plants due to salinity stress. The results of Zhang, *et al* (2001) [20] and Zhang and Blumwald (2001) [21] are in conformity of our findings that the transformation of *AtNHX1* gene enhanced salt tolerance than their control non transgenic counterparts in Brassica and tomato.

1. Root length (cm)

Root length of plants of both Asterix and Sante varieties at various NaCl treatments (Table-1) reacted significantly. All transgenic plant lines carrying *AtNHX1* gene in all plant lines of both potato varieties performed satisfactorily up to 60 mM NaCl while the non transformed wild type died after 2 weeks of NaCl stress application. Maximum root length (34.6 cm) was recorded in transgenic plant line A5 of Asterix followed by Sante plant line S5 (33.41 cm). S5 plants produced 28.58 cm root length and S7 produced 27.16 cm long roots while, S8 plants gave 27.08 cm long roots. A8 plants yielded 23.58 cm long roots. Wild type plants of Asterix i.e. A0, exhibited (8.83 cm) root length followed by wild type plants of Sante (S0) (10.0 cm) and were studied as the most susceptible among the examined plants to NaCl stress. Likewise, the different levels of NaCl also affected this parameter by producing maximum (31.37 cm) root length at 20 mM NaCl followed by 24.29 cm at 40 mM NaCl stress. However, 23.7 cm long roots were studied at control and 17.41 cm was observed at 60 mM NaCl stress concentration. Similarly root length of transgenic potato cultivars Asterix and Sante developed normally even at 60 mM NaCl while their counterpart wild type cultivars couldn't survived even a single week under stress. The findings of the Luming Trian, *et al.*, (2006) [22] that the integration of *AtNHX1* gene in tall fescue enhanced salt tolerance by producing normal plants even at 200 mM NaCl stress level.

2. Root Weight (g)

The investigated transgenic plants transformed with *AtNHX1* gene in the potato varieties Asterix and Sante for shoot weight plant⁻¹ at various levels of NaCl performed better than their wild type counterparts. Maximum (2.53 g) root weight plant⁻¹ was noted in transgenic potato line A7 of Asterix followed by transgenic Sante plant line S5 (1.78 g) whereas A5 produced 1.71 g and S7 showed 1.63 g root weight plant⁻¹. S8 produced 1.31 g while, A8 produced 1.013 g root weight plant⁻¹. Wild type control plants of Asterix (A0) showed 0.48 g whereas and wild type Sante (S0) produced minimum (0.23 gm) root weight plant⁻¹ to the applied NaCl stress. NaCl application at various levels also considerably affected non transgenic plants. However it was again observed that root weight of transgenic plants was increased at 20 mM NaCl. Maximum (1.68 gm) root weight plant⁻¹ was noted at 20 mM NaCl while at control (1.47 gm) root weight plant⁻¹ was observed. However, it was reduced to 1.01 gm at 40 mM and to 0.47 gm at 60 mM NaCl. The root weight plant⁻¹ was also drastically reduced in all transgenic plants but however they successfully survived and produced satisfactory growth and development. On the other hand, wild type potato cultivars were failed to tolerate even 20 mM NaCl stress. Aliakbar Askari, *et al.*, (2012) [23] revealed enhance root growth in genetically modified potato using *mltD* gene for salt tolerance. Also the results of Asif, *et al.*, (2011) [24] also confirmed salt tolerance in groundnut plants conferring *AtNHX1* gene.

3. Shoot weight (g)

Transgenic and wild type potato plants of both varieties Asterix and Sante showed highly significant differences for shoot weight plant⁻¹ at various levels of NaCl. Maximum (4.27 gm) shoot weight plant⁻¹ was studied in Sante event S5 followed by A5 and A7 (3.71 gm each) whereas produced S7 and S8 produced 3.14

gm and 3.12 gm shoot weight plant-1 respectively. A8 plants exhibited 2.66 gm shoot weight plant-1. Wild type non transgenic plants of A0 showed 0.56 gm whereas S0 produced minimum (0.53) shoot weight plant-1. NaCl stress induction at various levels also drastically affected non transgenic plants while the shoot weight of transgenic plants was increase at 20 mM NaCl level. Maximum (4.27 gm) shoot weight plant- was recorded at 20 mM NaCl while at control (3.47 gm) shoot weight plant-1. was recorded. However, it was reduced back to 1.66 gm at 40 mM and to 1.27 gm at 60 mM NaCl. In the same way the genetically modified potato varieties performed better than non transformed plants from both Asterix and Sante as well. Both varieties produced vigorous shoot development that lead to more shoot weight than control plants at NaCl stress condition. Muhammad Ashraf and Nudrat Aisha Akram (2009) [25] determined enhanced salt tolerance in plants due to *AtNHX1* gene transformation. Chen, *et al.*, (2007) [26] reported increased salt tolerance by satisfactory growth and development in maize plants due to transformation of *OsNHX1* gene.

4. Total Chlorophyll content (mg g⁻¹).

Chlorophyll content was determined by using the protocol of Arnon, (1949). Chlorophyll content of transgenic and wild type plants of variety Asterix and Sante was envisaged in this experiment to measure the tolerance of potato under different salt regimes (Table1). The maximum (13.47 mg g⁻¹) total chlorophyll was studied in transgenic Asterix plant line A7 followed by Transgenic Sante S5 (12.61 mg g⁻¹) while transgenic A5 revealed (12.49 mg g⁻¹) of chlorophyll. Transgenic plant line A8 formed 11.93 mg ml⁻¹ chlorophyll and transgenic line S8 plants showed 11.43 mg ml⁻¹ chlorophyll. On the other hand, S7 plants exhibited 9.06 mg g⁻¹ total chlorophyll. Here once again, the wild type plants S0 5.63 mg g⁻¹ and A0 demonstrated only 5.56 mg g⁻¹ of total chlorophyll. The effect of different levels of NaCl on total chlorophyll of transgenic and non transgenic plants of Asterix and Sante are given in Table 3. Maximum (15.39 mg ml⁻¹) chlorophyll content was observed at control. Increasing NaCl stress at higher concentrations, decreased chlorophyll content was recorded. Total chlorophyll was reduced to 11.66 mg g⁻¹ at 20 mM NaCl, 10.87 mg g⁻¹ at 40 mM and 8.97 mg g⁻¹ at 60 mM NaCl was studied. Our results are in strong conformity of the findings of Hui-Juan Gao, et al., (2014) [27] reported same results for decreased chlorophyll content in potato under stress. Mubshara Saadia *et al.* (2012) evaluated decreased chlorophyll in canola under salt stress [28].

5. Proline content (µg g⁻¹ FW)

Proline of all tested plants from transgenic and wild type Asterix and Santé have been given in Table 3.9. Maximum (3.12µg g⁻¹ FW) proline contents was studied in leaves of Asterix event A7 followed by A5 (3.02µg g⁻¹ FW) whereas S5 produced 2.33µg g⁻¹ FW. Although S7 plants exhibited 2.07µg g⁻¹ FW proline contents and S8 plants formed 1.71µg g⁻¹ FW. Wild type non transgenic plants of S0 expressed 0.17µg g⁻¹ FW proline contents, whereas, A0 showed 0.14µg g⁻¹ FW proline contents in their leaves. The levels of NaCl at and above 20 mM NaCl badly affected non transgenic plants while the proline contents of transgenic plants increased at each higher NaCl level. Maximum (3.09µg g⁻¹ FW) proline contents were observed at 60 mM NaCl whereas, (2.05µg g⁻¹ FW) proline contents were studied at 40 mM NaCl. In the same way, (1.72µg g⁻¹ FW) proline contents were noted at 20 mM NaCl. Finally minimum (0.04µg g⁻¹ FW) proline contents were studied at control that showed that, the production of proline in plants increases in the stress condition. Proline of all tested plants from transgenic and wild type Asterix and Santé have been studied in our research. The production of proline in plants increased under saline condition. Proline content was significantly higher in transgenic than non transgenic potato. Similar findings were reported by Hui-Juan Gao, et al., (2014) [29] by evaluation salt tolerance in potato and the amount of proline increases up to certain level. Suriyan Cha-um and Calermpol Kirdmanee (2009) [30] confirmed that proline accumulation enhanced salt stress in the canola plants.

6. Total soluble sugar analysis (TSS)

Total soluble sugar analysis was performed by following protocol of Dubois *et al* (1956) [31] with minor modifications. To evaluate the either the *ATNHX1* gene has manifested salt stress in transgenic potato lines, the

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3 weeks old plantlets from transgenic and non transgenic potato of both varieties were subjected to salt stress at (0, 20, 40, and 60 mM NaCl) in hydroponics. TSS of transgenic lines from Asterix and Sante with their non transgenic counterparts has been presented in (Table 3). The maximum (44.77 mg g⁻¹ FW) TSS content was recorded in leaves of Asterix plant line A8 followed by Sante plant line S8 (43.44 mg g⁻¹ FW) whereas plant line A5 and A7 exhibited 40.20 mg g⁻¹ FW and 37.08 mg g⁻¹ FW TSS. It was obvious that the non transgenic plant lines of both var. Asterix and Sante (A0 and S0) produced least (15.54 and 16.26 mg g⁻¹ FW) TSS. Total soluble sugar is one of the most important osmoprotectants that is manufactured by plants to get rid of any adverse environmental condition. The resistant plants develop its enormous quantity while, the susceptible plants can produce up to a certain level to sustain the environmental stress. In this study the TSS increased in the transgenic plants of potato than the non transgenic plants. The ANOVA also showed significant results for TSS in the tested potato lines under NaCl stress environment (Table 3). Our findings are in strong correlation of the assessment of Aghai *et al*, (2008) [32] who investigated elevated concentration of TSS in potato under salt stress and also Farhad *et al*, (2011) [33] are in line with our conclusions who reported enhanced levels of TSS in potato under different stress regimes of drought.

7. Na⁺ /K⁺ content (mg g⁻¹)

Na⁺ content of plants either transgenic or non transgenic have been shown in Table 3.10. Maximum (0.67 mg g⁻¹) Na⁺ content was recorded in leaves of Sante event S5 and Asterix event A5 (0.66 mg g⁻¹). A7 produced (0.57 mg g⁻¹) Na⁺, whereas A8 gave 0.56 mg g⁻¹ Na⁺ in leaves. S7 plants showed 0.53 mg g⁻¹ while S8 plants formed 0.55 mg g⁻¹ Na⁺. Control plants of A0 expressed 0.15 mg g⁻¹ Na⁺ in leaves, whereas, S0 depicted 0.13 mg g⁻¹ Na⁺ contents in leaves. Maximum (0.71 mg g⁻¹) Na⁺ content were noted at 60 mM NaCl whereas, (0.54 mg g⁻¹) Na⁺ content were recorded at 40 mM NaCl. Consequently, (0.49 mg g⁻¹) Na⁺ content were observed at 20 mM NaCl. In contrast, minimum (0.17 mg g⁻¹) Na⁺ contents were noticed at control that revealed that, the production of Na⁺ contents in plant leaves increases in the stress condition. K⁺ content in leaves of both transgenic and non transgenic Asterix and Sante have been shown in Table 3.11. Maximum (0.53 mg g⁻¹) K⁺ was observed in leaves of Sante event S5 followed by S8 (0.52 mg g⁻¹) K⁺ whereas, Asterix A7 and A8 depicted (0.51 mg g⁻¹ each) K⁺ content. S7 plants showed 0.46 mg g⁻¹ K⁺. A5 plants expressed 0.39 mg g⁻¹ K⁺ content. In contrast the control plants of A0 expressed 0.23 mg g⁻¹ K⁺, whereas, S0 depicted 0.20 mg g⁻¹ K⁺ contents up to 60 mM NaCl stress level.

Here, the effect of NaCl at different levels on K⁺ content is given in Table 3. Maximum (0.45 mg g⁻¹) K⁺ content was observed at 20 mM NaCl whereas, (0.43 mg g⁻¹) K⁺ content were noted at 60 mM NaCl. Consequently, (0.41 mg g⁻¹) K⁺ content were studied at 40 mM NaCl. On the other hand, minimum (0.39 mg g⁻¹) K⁺ content were detected at control. In the mean time, S7 presented (0.25 mg g⁻¹) K⁺ contents at control, by increasing NaCl to 20 mM, the plants accumulated (0.41 mg g⁻¹) K⁺ contents and 0.53 mg g⁻¹ K⁺ at 40 mM and 0.54 mg g⁻¹ K⁺ at 60 mM NaCl. The same way, S8 expressed 0.40 mg g⁻¹ K⁺ content at control while, the plants displayed increased amount of (0.51 mg g⁻¹) of K⁺ at 20 mM NaCl stress, where they additionally accumulated (0.57 mg g⁻¹) K⁺ contents at 40 mM and 0.63 mg g⁻¹ K⁺ contents at 60 mM NaCl. Then again, non transgenic S0 plants expressed exhibited 0.36 mg g⁻¹ K⁺ contents at control that was increased to 0.44 mg g⁻¹ K⁺ at 20 mM NaCl. In other way, these plants had not grown for more than two weeks at 40 mM and 60 mM NaCl. The effect of NaCl at different levels on accumulation of Na⁺ and K⁺ content in leaves of both transgenic and control plants revealed that, the production of Na⁺ contents in plant leaves increased in the stress condition. Our findings are in strong conformity of that Na⁺ and K⁺ content increased in potato plants under salt stress. Amal A. Mohamed *et al* (2010) revealed that the transgenic potato showed greater salt tolerance by accumulation more Na⁺ contents than the non transgenic potato. Suriyan Cha-um and Calermpol Kirdmanee (2009) [34] confirmed that proline accumulation enhanced salt stress in the canola plants.

8. K⁺/Na⁺ ratio determination

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The effect of NaCl on the growth and development of transgenic and non transgenic Asterix and Sante potato varieties in the hydroponics significantly affected the K^{+1}/Na^{+1} ratio. The survival rate of transgenic potato plantlets under NaCl stress showed greater K^{+1}/Na^{+1} ratio in hydroponic culture. The AVOVA Table-1 also depicted highly significant differences amongst the tested potato lines (transgenic and non transgenic) in both varieties. By increasing the NaCl stress in the hydroponic, K^{+1}/Na^{+1} ratio increased simultaneously at every higher level in all transgenic and non transgenic potato lines. The maximum (1.86) K^{+1}/Na^{+1} ratio was noted in Asterix transgenic line A5 followed by Asterix transgenic line A3 (1.29) whereas, minimum (0.87) was recorded in Asterix non transgenic line (A0) followed by non transgenic Sante line S0 (1.03) K^{+1}/Na^{+1} ratio. The NaCl at higher concentration raised the K^{+1}/Na^{+1} ratio in all potato plants leaves. The highest (2.4) mean value for K^{+}/Na^{+} ratio was recorded at 60 mM NaCl and the lowest (0.66) K^{+1}/Na^{+1} ratio as noted at control. Similarly the K^{+1}/Na^{+1} ratio was higher due to more accumulation of these nutrients at 20 mM (0.81) and at 40 mM (0.93).

Conclusion:

Under this study the transgenic potato variety Asterix carrying *AtNHX1* gene performed far better than that of non transgenic counterpart to salt stress up to 60 mM NaCl with normally developed growth parameters and satisfactory results in physiological parameters. Also its performance was more satisfactory than transgenic potato variety Sante. *Hydroponic system* has been evolved as an easy approach to assess salt stress tolerance in transgenic and their wild type *in vitro* produced potato plantlets.

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Table 2. ANOVA for the assessment of NaCl at different levels on the Physio-morphological characters of transgenic and non transgenic potato lines.

S.O.V	Mean squares											
	D.F	Plant height	Nodes plant-1	Root length	Root weight	Shoot weight	Chlorophyll	Proline	TSS	Na	K	Ka:Na
Plant Line	7	576.07	63.939	1150.69	6.37	17.28	119.97	15.64				
1956.21	0.549	0.22	0.6475									
Treatments	3	1089.71	210.205	781.95	6.56	33.06	400.05	39.10	2638.10			
1.225	0.018	22.3426										
Plant line x Treatment	21	62.54	16.030	94.31	1.58	5.71	31.89	2.65	207.00			
0.140	0.084	1.2933										
Error	6	2.94	2.488	6.28	0.01	0.051	0.41	0.004	2.12			
0.001	0.0005	0.0885										
Total	95											